

Genetic risk score for coronary artery calcification and its predictive ability for coronary artery disease

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The modest added predictive value of the existing genetic risk scores (GRSs) for coronary artery disease (CAD) could be partly due to missing genetic components, hidden in the genetic architecture of intermediate

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Coronary artery disease
Prediction

phenotypes such as coronary artery calcification (CAC). In this study, we investigated the predictive ability of CAC GRS for CAD.

Materials and methods: We investigated the association of CAC GRSs with CAD and coronary calcification among the participants in the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health study (LURIC) ($n = 2742$), the Tampere Vascular Study (TVS) ($n = 133$), and the Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS) ($n = 660$) using summary data from the largest multi-ancestry GWAS meta-analysis of CAC to date. Added predictive value of the CAC GRS over the traditional CVD risk factors as well as metaGRS, a GRS for CAD constructed with 1.7 million genetic variants, was tested with standard train–test machine learning approach using the LURIC data, which had the largest sample size.

Results: CAC GRS was significantly associated with CAD in LURIC (OR=1.41, 95 % CI [1.28–1.55]), TVS (OR=1.79, 95 % CI [1.05–3.21]) as well as in TSDS (OR=4.20, 95 % CI [1.74–10.52]). CAC GRS showed strong association with calcification areas in left (OR=1.78, 95 % CI [1.16–2.74]) and right (OR=1.71, 95 % CI [1.98–2.67]) coronary arteries. There was statistically significant added predictive value of the CAC GRS for CAD over the used traditional CVD risk factors (AUC 0.734 vs 0.717, p -value = 0.02). Furthermore, CAC GRS improved the prediction accuracy for CAD when combined with metaGRS.

Conclusions: This study showed that CAC GRS is a new risk marker for CAD in three European cohorts, with added predictive value over the traditional CVD risk factors.

1. Background

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a key global public health issue with major economic as well as human costs globally [1]. A major focus on prevention of CVDs is crucial to achieve the United Nations member states' commitment to a 25 % reduction in premature CVD mortality by 2025 [2]. Atherosclerosis, the underlying pathology behind most CVDs, begins decades before the clinical manifestations and silently reaches a stage where it can only be slowed down but not be reversed [3]. Identifying individuals at an early stage of the cardiovascular (CV) cascade who do not yet have symptoms (subclinical atherosclerosis) is of high importance in preventive cardiology.

Genetic risk score (GRS) is a system-level approach that combines single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) to enhance the predictive ability for a polygenic disease [4]. GRS is an attractive target as a potential predictor because these genetic variants remain stable across the lifespan and can thus provide information on an individual's disease predisposition from birth and early age to old age. Several genome-wide association studies (GWASs) have characterized the genetic makeup of CVDs, including atherosclerosis-related [5] and coronary artery disease (CAD)-related SNPs [6]. A GRS calculated with all validated CVD-related SNPs may also predict CVDs in the early stages. However, the SNPs identified so far with traditional GWASs explain only a small fraction (10–20 %) of CVD heritability [6–8]. The identification of SNPs explaining the missing heritability is important for a robust GRS and, therefore, constitutes a crucial step forward for the early prediction of CVD. The utility of GRS in CVD risk prediction models is still in the early phase. The modest added predictive value shown by recent studies such as by [9] could partly be due to the missing genetic components hidden within the genetic architecture of intermediate phenotypes of CVD, such as coronary artery calcification (CAC), that are involved in the pathogenesis of CVD. Indeed, although there is shared etiology between CVD and CAC, a recent comprehensive GWAS study of CAC found several new CAC associated genes that have so far not been reported to be associated with CVD [10]. CAC score, a measure of the amount of calcified plaque in coronary arteries, is a highly reliable indicator of cardiovascular disease beyond the established CVD risk variables [11,12]. According to the American College of Cardiology (ACC)/ American Heart Association (AHA) guidelines, CAC scores are useful in directing treatment for those with intermediate risk of cardiovascular events [13]. However, CAC increases with age and therefore CAC test is not recommended for younger individuals as detectable calcification of the lipid rich plaques takes time. Genetic variants identified with GWAS of CAC might help in developing GRS with CAC equivalent predictive ability for CVD. The ability to predict CVD utilizing CAC GRS can have important ramifications for optimizing lifestyle practices in primary prevention.

The main objective of the current study was to investigate whether

GRS for CAC (CAC GRS), calculated using GWAS summary statistics of independent lead SNPs from 11 different loci associated with CAC from the most recent GWAS [10], is associated with angiographically or morphometrically verified CAD in three European cohorts. We aimed to confirm the link between CAC associated SNPs and calcification by studying the association of CAC GRS with calcification areas measured in autopsy coronary arteries. In addition to the association study of the CAC GRS with CAD, we also assessed its added predictive value for CAD over the traditional CVD risk factors (age, sex, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, systolic blood pressure, treatment for hypertension and smoking habit) that are included in the Framingham risk score (FRS) [14]. Furthermore, we assessed added predictive value of CAC GRS, a simple GRS for an intermediate phenotype constructed with only 11 SNPs, over metaGRS, a relatively more complex GRS for CAD constructed with 1.7 million SNPs [15]. We believe that findings from such an assessment may help in confirming the assumption that GRS of an intermediate phenotype such as CAC may help in improving GRS for CAD, due to their direct association with the clinical outcome as compared to a GRS of a broader disease end point such as CAD [16].

2. Methods

2.1. Study participants

This study was based on three European cohorts – the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study, the Tampere Vascular Study (TVS) and the Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS). The LURIC study comprises of 3316 European patients referred to the Cardiac Center Ludwigshafen (Germany) for invasive coronary angiography between July 1997 and January 2000 [17]. Clinical indications for angiography were chest pain or a positive non-invasive stress test suggestive of myocardial ischemia. To limit clinical heterogeneity, individuals suffering from acute illnesses other than acute coronary syndrome (ACS), chronic non-cardiac diseases and a history of malignancy within the five past years were excluded. The study protocol was approved by the ethics committee of the 'Landesärztekammer Rheinland-Pfalz' [#837.255.97(1394)]. The present study is based on 2742 patients (women: 29 %), aged 17–92 years, who had genotype data as well as CAD and traditional CVD risk factors data used in this study. The patients with 50 % or more stenosis in one of the major coronary arteries were defined as CAD cases.

Tampere Vascular Study (TVS) constitutes individuals at high risk of cardiovascular diseases, events and deaths who have undergone an exercise stress test at Tampere University Hospital [18]. This study was based on genotype data from a subpopulation of 133 individuals with 98 angiographically verified cases of CAD followed-up during 2008. The patients with at least 50 % stenosis in either left main coronary artery,

left anterior descending (LAD) coronary artery or right coronary artery were defined as CAD cases. The participants were 38–80 years old and 29 % of them were women. The study has been approved by the Ethics Committee of Tampere Hospital District. All studies were conducted according to the declaration of Helsinki, with the informed consent from individual patient involved.

The Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS) consists of cross-sectional population autopsy samples of deaths occurring out of hospital for any reason. This study involved 660 cases who had both genetic data and coronary measurements available. Computer-assisted morphometry (Olympus Cell-D software) was used to measure the percentage area of calcified lesions from the five centimeters long piece of the proximal part of the LAD and right coronary arteries (RCA). The stenosis percentage was measured from microscopic sections of the coronary arteries. TSDS cases with 50 % or more stenosis in either LAD coronary artery including left main part of the artery or RCA were defined as CAD cases. The participants were aged 18–94 years and 28 % of them were women. The CVD risk factor data such as smoking and hypertension were collected by interviewing a spouse, a relative, or a close friend of the deceased. The permission to collect the data was obtained from the ethical committee of Tampere University hospital (Permission number R09097) and from the National Supervisory Authority for Welfare and Health.

2.2. Traditional CVD risk factor measurements

Traditional risk factors for CVD included in this study were age, sex, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, smoking habit, systolic blood pressure and hypertension treatment. The assay methods have been reported in detail previously for the LURIC participants [17] and for the TVS participants [18]. The selection of the risk factors was based on the six coronary risk factors used in the Framingham risk score [14]. Only age, sex, and body mass index (BMI) were available CVD risk factors in the TSDS, whereas data on smoking habit and hypertension were gathered via postal questionnaire from spouses or close relatives and were available for 228 (34.5 %) out of the 660 participants.

2.3. Genotyping, quality control and genotype imputation

Genomic DNA for the LURIC study participants was prepared from EDTA anticoagulated peripheral blood by means of a common salting-out procedure. The Affymetrix Genome-Wide Human SNP Array 6.0 was used for genotyping. Genomic DNA for the TVS was extracted from peripheral blood leukocytes using QIAamp DNA Blood Minikit and automated biorobot M48 extraction (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Genotyping was done using the Illumina HumanHap660W-Quad BeadChip according to the manufacturer's recommendation. In TSDS, DNA was extracted from postmortem blood using a Qiagen DNA extraction kit. Illumina HumanCoreExome-12 were used as genotyping platform and genotypes were called with Illumina GenCall algorithm. The quality control filters applied to the LURIC genotype data included: sample call rate < 0.95, SNP call rate < 0.98, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium test p -value < 1×10^{-4} , and minor allele frequency < 0.01. Genotype imputation was completed with the Haplotype Reference Consortium (HRC) imputation panel as a reference. The quality control filters applied for the TVS and TSDS included: sample and SNP call rate < 0.95, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium test p -value < 10^{-6} , and minor allele frequency < 5 %. Genotype imputation in both TVS and TSDS was performed using SNPTEST v2.3.0 and 1000 Genomes phase 1 version 3 haplotypes as reference. All the 11 independent SNPs used in the construction of CAC GRS in all the three cohorts had a squared correlation > 0.30 between imputed and true genotypes.

2.4. Biostatistical analysis

All biostatistical analyses and data processing were performed using

the statistical package R version 4.1.0 [19]. The CAC GRSs in all the three cohorts (LURIC, TVS and TSDS) were calculated using GWAS summary statistics of independent lead SNPs from 11 different loci associated with CAC [10] as sum of effect allele dosages or counts of the 11 SNPs weighted by their corresponding effect sizes [Table S1-S2]. The CAC GRS was standardized to have zero mean and unit standard deviation. Association of the CAC GRS with CAD in the LURIC, TVS and TSDS participants was tested using three logistic regression models, i) adjusted for age, sex and BMI (model 1), ii) adjusted for traditional coronary risk factors used in the FRS, namely age, sex, smoking status, HDL cholesterol, total cholesterol, systolic blood pressure and treatment for hypertension [14] (model 2), and iii) model 2 adjusted additionally for metaGRS (model 3). MetaGRS is a GRS for CAD based on 1745,179 genetic variants associated with CAD and its construction is described in detail elsewhere [15]. We matched the 1745,179 genetic variants in the genetic data from the three cohorts in this study. The summary statistics of the genetic variants was downloaded from the polygenic score (PGS) catalog [<https://www.pgscatalog.org/score/PGS000018/>] and metaGRSs for the three cohorts were then calculated using the same method used to calculate CAC GRS [Supplementary Section S2]. Additionally, the models 2 and 3 in LURIC and TVS were also adjusted for the first five principal components of the genetic data to adjust for potential bias due to population structure and statin usage. Model 2 in TSDS was adjusted for age, sex, BMI, smoking, hypertension and the first five principal components of the genetic data. Measurement data on clinical lipids, blood pressure and statin usage were not available among the TSDS participants. Association of CAC GRS with calcified plaque percentage in LAD as well as RCA of the TSDS participants was tested using beta regression models using *betareg* R package [20]. The analyses were adjusted for age, sex, BMI, smoking, hypertension and the first five principal components of the genetic data. All the association analyses were also conducted by dividing the CAC GRS and metaGRS into five quantiles, with the 0–0.25 quantile as reference. Furthermore, sex- and age-stratified association analysis between CAC GRS and CAD was also conducted, however, using only LURIC data as it has the largest sample size among the three cohorts.

Added predictive ability of the CAC GRS over the traditional CVD risk factors and metaGRS was assessed using the LURIC data. A reference prediction model for CAD including only the traditional CVD risk factors as predictors was built. Then, the added predictive value of the CAC GRS for CAD was assessed by comparing logistic regression-based prediction model including the traditional CVD risk factors and CAC GRS (test prediction model 1) with the reference prediction model as described elsewhere [21]. For comparison, we also assessed the added predictive value of the metaGRS by comparing prediction model including the traditional CVD risk factors and metaGRS (test prediction model 2) with the reference prediction model. Then, we assessed the improvement in added predictive value obtained by combining CAC GRS and metaGRS by comparing prediction model including the traditional CVD risk factors, CAC GRS and metaGRS (test prediction model 3) with the reference prediction model. Assessment of the predictive values was performed using a standard train-test split machine learning approach, i) fitting models to training data (70 % data), ii) testing the models on test data (30 % data), and iii) calculating the area under the receiver operating curve (AUC) for assessment of the predictive model. The variance of AUC was estimated by repeating the model fitting and validation for 1000 bootstraps of the original data. Added predictive values of the CAC GRS, metaGRS and CAC GRS–metaGRS combined, over the traditional CVD risk factors was tested by taking differences between AUCs (Δ AUC) obtained from the reference and test prediction models over 1000 bootstraps of the original data. The statistical significance of the difference (p -value) was estimated by counting the proportion of Δ AUC less than zero. Potential bias in results due to higher number of cases as compared to controls in LURIC was investigated by repeating the analysis with a version of LURIC data with balanced number of cases and controls, generated by implementing under sampling technique

implemented in *unbalanced* R package [22].

3. Results

3.1. Study population characteristics

Clinical characteristics of the study participants from the LURIC, TVS and TSDS cohorts are presented in Table 1. A total of 2742 individuals had complete data on genetics, angiographically verified CAD and traditional CVD risk factors in LURIC. In TVS, 133 participants had complete data on genetics, angiographically verified CAD and traditional CVD risk factors. In case of TSDS, there were 622 participants with complete data on genetics, morphometrically verified CAD, calcified plaque area percentage in the LAD and RCA, age, sex and BMI. Data on smoking habit and medication for hypertension was available for 228 out of the 622 TSDS participants. Data from all the three cohorts, stratified by case-control, is presented in Table 1.

3.2. Association of CAC GRS with CAD in LURIC, TVS and TSDS cohorts

The CAC GRSs were associated with CAD in all the three cohorts [Supplementary Figures S1-S3]. In LURIC, CAC GRS was associated with angiographically verified CAD in both model 1 (OR of 1.45, 95 % CI [1.33–1.59]) and model 2 (OR=1.41, 95 % CI [1.28–1.55]) [Table 2]. Among the traditional CVD risk factors, age, sex, HDL cholesterol, smoking habit and medication for hypertension were associated with CAD with statistical significance of p -value < 0.05. In TVS, CAC GRS was associated with angiographically verified CAD in both model 1 (OR=1.64, 95 % CI [1.08–2.56]) and model 2 (OR=1.79, 95 % CI [1.05–3.21]). Besides the CAC GRS, age, sex, total cholesterol, smoking habit and medication for hypertension were associated with CAD with statistical significance of p -value < 0.05. Similarly, in TSDS, CAC GRS was associated with CAD in both model 1 (OR=2.96, 95 % CI [1.79–4.97]) and model 2 (OR=4.20, 95 % CI [1.74–10.52]). Among the traditional risk factors included in the models, only age was associated

with CAD with statistical significance (p -value= 1.2×10^{-05}). The association between CAC GRS and CAD remained statistically significant even after adjusting for metaGRS in model 3 in LURIC (OR=1.17, 95 % CI [1.06–1.30]) and TSDS (OR=3.31, 95 % CI [1.29–8.76]), but not in TVS (OR=1.36, 95 % CI [0.73–2.64]). The association analyses were repeated for male and female participants separately among LURIC participants. While the association between CAC GRS and CAD among males remained similar to the one obtained from the whole population, there was no statistically significant association between CAC GRS and CAD in model 3 among females [Supplementary Tables S3-S4]. Similarly, the analyses were also repeated for LURIC participants aged 40 years and above. The results obtained from this age group were also similar to that obtained from the whole LURIC participants [Supplementary Tables S5]. However, there were only 74 LURIC participants aged below 40 years and there was no statistically significant association between CAC GRS and CAD in this group.

The association analysis was also conducted by dividing the CAC GRS and metaGRS into five quantiles, with the 0–0.25 quantile as reference. As expected, we observed a gradient of CAD risk across the four quantile intervals, with the highest number of CAD cases in the [0.75–1] interval for both CAC GRS and metaGRS in all the three studies cohorts [Fig. 1]. In LURIC, the risk of CAD in the highest quantile interval [0.75–1] was 1.48-fold higher as compared to the control population (OR=1.48, 95 % CI [1.10–1.98]) after adjusting for metaGRS and the traditional risk factors in model 3. Similarly, in TSDS, the risk of CAD in the highest quantile interval [0.75–1] was 2.79-fold higher as compared to the control population (OR=2.79, 95 % CI [1.15–6.95]). However, there was no statistically significant association between CAC GRS quantiles and CAD in TVS in model 3.

3.3. Association of CAC GRS with calcified plaque area percentage in TSDS participants

We assessed association of the CAC GRS with calcified plaque area percentage in the LAD and RCA of the TSDS participants. There was

Table 1
Clinical characteristics of the study cohorts.

Variables	LURIC			TVS			TSDS		
	CAD Cases	Controls	P-value	CAD Cases	Controls	P-value	CAD Cases	Controls	P-value
Number of subjects (%)	1912 (70)	830 (30)	–	98 (74)	35 (26)	–	327 (53)	295 (47)	–
Female (%)	425 (22)	367 (44)	–	28 (29)	10 (29)	–	79 (24)	74 (25)	–
Age, years	64 (29–92)	60 (17–88)	8.8×10^{-16}	60 (39–80)	56 (38–72)	0.01	69 (24–95)	58 (17–95)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	27.4 (16.3–46.2)	27.6 (16.7–46.1)	0.3	27.8 (18.9–41.3)	27.5 (18.7–36.9)	0.8	28.7 (16.4–54.1)	28.9 (14.6–64.9)	0.7
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	142.3 (76.7–230)	138.6 (73.7–228.3)	7.2×10^{-05}	134.9 (86–192)	135.1 (104–176)	0.97	–	–	–
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	205.2 (100–442)	215.2 (79–453)	2.4×10^{-08}	94.1 (55.8–135)	100 (72.0–151.2)	0.2	–	–	–
HDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	37.1 (2–104)	41.5 (15–91)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$	25.4 (12.2–55.6)	26.6 (13.9–38.9)	0.4	–	–	–
LDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	114.4 (20–329)	120.9 (21–361)	4.7×10^{-06}	56.8 (19.8–95.4)	62.0 (36–99)	0.09	–	–	–
Smoking (%)	1337 (70)	423 (51)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$	61 (62)	21 (60)	0.97	68/130 (52)	56/98 (57)	0.64
Medication for hypertension	1185 (62)	431 (52)	1.1×10^{-06}	93 (95)	28 (80)	0.02	88/130 (68)	52/98 (53)	0.008
Statin usage	1138 (60)	176 (21)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$	81 (83)	11 (31)	6×10^{-08}	–	–	–
Stenosis in LAD (%)	–	–	–	–	–	–	61.5 (5–100)	24.7 (0–49.3)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Stenosis in RCA (%)	–	–	–	–	–	–	52.5 (0–100)	18.4 (0–49.2)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Calcium in LAD (%)	–	–	–	–	–	–	28.9 (0–100)	6.3 (0–79.1)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Calcium in RCA (%)	–	–	–	–	–	–	25.7 (0–100)	4.3 (0–88.8)	$<2.2 \times 10^{-16}$

Definitions: Patients with 50 % or more stenosis in one of the major coronary arteries were defined as CAD cases in both LURIC and TVS cohorts. Autopsy cases with 50 % or more stenosis in either left anterior descending (LAD) coronary artery including left main part of the artery or right coronary artery (RCA) were defined as CAD cases in the TSDS cohort.

Abbreviations: LURIC, the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health Study; TVS, the Tampere Vascular Study; TSDS, the Tampere Sudden Death Study; CAD, Coronary Artery Disease.

Table 2

Association of the genetic risk score for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) and clinical cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk factors with coronary artery disease (CAD) in the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study, Tampere Vascular Study (TVS) and Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS) participants.

Risk factors	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	OR (95 % CI)	P-value	OR (95 % CI)	P-value	OR (95 % CI)	P-value
The Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study						
Age	1.05 (1.04–1.05)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	1.05 (1.04–1.06)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	1.06 (1.05–1.07)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$
Sex (male)	3.49 (2.90–4.21)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	2.70 (2.16–3.39)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	3.13 (2.47–3.97)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$
Body mass index (BMI)	0.99 (0.97–1.01)	0.26	–	–	–	–
Systolic blood pressure	–	–	1.00 (1.00–1.01)	0.19	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.14
Total cholesterol	–	–	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.32	1.00 (0.99–1.00)	0.44
HDL cholesterol	–	–	0.98 (0.97–0.99)	5.9×10^{-07}	0.98 (0.97–0.99)	4.6×10^{-06}
Smoking habit (yes)	–	–	1.83 (1.48–2.26)	1.7×10^{-08}	1.74 (1.39–2.17)	8.6×10^{-07}
Hypertension medication (yes)	–	–	1.32 (1.07–1.63)	0.008	1.23 (0.99–1.53)	0.07
CAC GRS	1.45 (1.33–1.59)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	1.41 (1.28–1.55)	3.6×10^{-12}	1.17 (1.06–1.30)	0.002
metaGRS	–	–	–	–	2.11 (1.89–2.37)	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$
The Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS)						
Age	1.05 (1.04–1.07)	3.9×10^{-16}	1.06 (1.03–1.08)	1.2×10^{-5}	1.06 (1.03–1.09)	5.9×10^{-6}
Sex (male)	1.52 (1.01–2.28)	0.04	1.29 (0.65–2.57)	0.5	1.30 (0.66–2.59)	0.5
Body mass index (BMI)	1.01 (0.98–1.04)	0.5	1.02 (0.97–1.07)	0.5	1.02 (0.97–1.07)	0.5
Systolic blood pressure	–	–	–	–	–	–
Total cholesterol	–	–	–	–	–	–
HDL cholesterol	–	–	–	–	–	–
Smoking habit (yes)	–	–	1.87 (0.97–3.71)	0.06	1.83 (0.95–3.64)	0.08
Hypertension medication (yes)	–	–	1.29 (0.67–2.47)	0.4	1.25 (0.65–2.39)	0.5
CAC GRS	2.96 (1.79–4.97)	3.1×10^{-05}	4.20 (1.74–10.52)	0.002	3.31 (1.29–8.76)	0.01
metaGRS	–	–	–	–	1.66 (0.82–3.41)	0.16
The Tampere Vascular Study (TVS)						
Age	1.06 (1.01–1.11)	0.02	1.07 (1.01–1.15)	0.04	1.10 (1.05–1.19)	0.01
Sex (male)	0.86 (0.34–2.10)	0.75	4.94 (1.26–23.62)	0.03	1.19 (0.75–1.75)	0.13
Body mass index (BMI)	1.03 (0.94–1.13)	0.59	–	–	–	–
Systolic blood pressure	–	–	1.01 (0.98–1.04)	0.51	1.00 (0.97–1.04)	0.91
Total cholesterol	–	–	0.48 (0.25–0.85)	0.02	0.45 (0.21–0.84)	0.02
HDL cholesterol	–	–	0.84 (0.16–4.57)	0.83	1.11 (0.20–7.16)	0.91
Smoking habit (yes)	–	–	3.46 (1.07–12.24)	0.04	2.98 (0.80–1.20)	0.11
Hypertension medication (yes)	–	–	6.79 (1.26–41.1)	0.03	6.42 (0.76–5.68)	0.08
CAC GRS	1.64 (1.08–2.56)	0.02	1.79 (1.05–3.21)	0.04	1.36 (0.73–2.64)	0.34
metaGRS	–	–	–	–	4.31 (1.86–12.5)	0.002

Abbreviations: OR, odd ratio; CI, confidence interval.

statistically significant association between the CAC GRS and calcified plaque area in both LAD (OR=1.78, 95 % CI [1.16–2.74]) and RCA (OR=1.71, 95 % CI [1.09–2.67]) after adjusting for age, sex, BMI, smoking habit, hypertension and the first five principal components of the genetic data [Table 3]. An increasing gradient in calcified plaque area as well as stenosis percentage in both LAD and RCA was observed across the four quantile intervals of CAC GRS and metaGRS [Fig. 2]. These results, therefore, suggest that CAC GRS is a significant predictor of coronary calcification along with age, sex and hypertension.

3.4. Assessment of added predictive value of CAC GRS over traditional CVD risk factors

There was statistically significant added predictive value of the CAC GRS over the traditional CVD risk factors (AUC 0.734 vs 0.717, p-value = 0.02) used in this study [Fig. 3]. Similarly, there was statistically significant added predictive value of the metaGRS over the traditional CVD risk factors (AUC 0.784 vs 0.717, p-value = 0.001). Combination of CAC GRS and metaGRS resulted into mildly improved added predictive value over the traditional risk factors (AUC 0.787 vs 0.717, p-value = 0.001). Results from the same analysis repeated with the version of LURIC data with balanced number of cases and controls were similar. There was statistically significant added predictive value of both the CAC GRS (AUC 0.739 vs 0.721, p-value = 0.04), and metaGRS (AUC 0.788 vs 0.721, p-value = 0.001). Also, combination of CAC GRS and metaGRS improved the added predictive value for CAD over the traditional risk factors (AUC 0.791 vs 0.721, p-value = 0.001).

4. Discussion

We found statistically significant associations of CAC GRS with CAD in all the three European cohorts studied in this study. We also demonstrated that CAC GRS has statistically significant added predictive value for CAD over the traditionally used CVD risk factors and that combination of CAC GRS with metaGRS might improve prediction accuracy for CAD. These findings suggest that the genetic variants regulating coronary artery calcification may be used as a tool for CVD risk prediction. Moreover, we found that CAC GRS is significantly associated with morphometrically measured coronary calcification areas, which confirms the earlier findings on the association between CAC related genes and coronary calcification measured with computed tomography at the vessel wall level [10].

There is consistent evidence suggesting that a predictive value of GRS for CVDs may have clinical utility [23]. Efforts to develop or improve existing GRS for CVD risk prediction is important because a robust GRS with high predictability has a potential to shift the paradigm in prevention approaches of CVD. Optimization of the GRS for CVD prediction is crucial to achieve the aimed progress in primordial prevention of CVD [24].

The underlying hypothesis of this study was that a part of the missing heritability of CVD might be explained by SNPs associated with intermediate phenotypes of CVD such as CAC [25]. CAC is a highly predictive CVD risk marker in asymptomatic individuals that can provide additional predictive value over the traditional CVD risk factors [11,12]. Investigation of the genetic architecture of CAC may reveal SNPs that are critical to understanding the genetic basis of CVD. A recent study showed that the progression of CAC is associated with GRS for both CAD and CAC [26]. The CAC GRS in that study was based on only three SNPs

Fig. 1. Distribution of the coronary artery disease (CAD) cases across the four quantile intervals of genetic risk score for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) (upper panel) and metaGRS (lower panel) in the three studied cohorts. *Abbreviations:* LURIC, the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health Study; TVS, the Tampere Vascular Study; TSDS, the Tampere Sudden Death Study; CAD, Coronary Artery Disease.

Table 3

Association of the genetic risk score for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) with calcified plaque area percentage in the left anterior descending (LAD) and right coronary arteries (RCA).

Risk factors	Calcified plaque area percentage in the LAD		Calcified plaque area percentage in the RCA	
	OR (95 % CI)	P-value	OR (95 % CI)	P-value
Age	1.03 (1.02–1.04)	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁹	1.02 (1.01–1.04)	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁵
Sex (male)	1.53 (1.09–2.13)	0.01	1.35 (0.96–1.90)	0.08
Body mass index (BMI)	0.99 (0.97–1.01)	0.4	1.00 (0.98–1.03)	0.7
Smoking habit (yes)	1.06 (0.77–1.46)	0.7	1.09 (0.79–1.52)	0.6
Hypertension (yes)	1.62 (1.17–2.24)	0.004	1.53 (1.10–2.15)	0.01
CAC GRS	1.78 (1.16–2.74)	0.009	1.71 (1.09–2.67)	0.02

Abbreviations: OR, odd ratio; CI, confidence interval.

associated with CAC. To our knowledge, there has been no other studies investigating association of CAC GRS with CAD and calcified plaque area.

In this study, we explored whether SNPs associated with CAC, when aggregated as a CAC GRS, are associated with CAD. The findings of this study suggest that CAC GRS might be a useful CVD risk marker with statistically significant added predictive value over the traditionally used risk factors and coronary calcified plaque area. An important

benefit of CAC GRS over CAC is that the former is stable throughout the lifespan and therefore can play impactful role in primary prevention of CVD by lifestyle modification, in decision making for early statin therapy or in prioritizing patients for CAC scan [27–30]. Our results suggest that CAC GRS has added benefit in predicting CAD beyond traditional risk factors. Importantly, CAC GRS appears to improve prediction accuracy of metaGRS, albeit mildly, despite being constructed with only 11 independent SNPs, in contrast to 1.7 million SNPs used to construct metaGRS. Such significant association of CAC GRS with CAD supports the assumption that GRS of an intermediate phenotype have direct association with the clinical outcome as compared to a GRS constructed with SNPs associated with broader disease end point such as CAD [16]. Furthermore, these findings shed light upon common etiologies of CAD and CAC.

This study has some limitations. Some of the traditional CVD risk factors such as systolic blood pressure, HDL cholesterol, total cholesterol and information about statin usage were not available for the autopsy based TSDS participants. Furthermore, due to missing response rate characteristic of postal surveys, data on smoking habit and medication for hypertension was available for only one-third-of the participants. Therefore, considering the intriguing results in this study, studies with larger sample size is warranted. Also, while both TVS and LURIC study include participants with high risk of cardiovascular disease, TSDS consists of cross-sectional population autopsy samples of deaths occurring out of hospital for any reason. Therefore, as our findings may not be representative for otherwise asymptomatic community, population-based studies on this topic are warranted. Furthermore, all the three cohorts included in this study are of European origin, and therefore, studies with populations of different ethnicities are needed.

Fig. 2. Boxplots showing calcified plaque area percentage in the left anterior descending (LAD) and right coronary arteries (RCA) and stenosis percentage across the four quartile intervals of genetic risk score for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) (upper panel) and metaGRS (lower panel) in the Tampere Sudden Death Study (TSDS).

Fig. 3. A. Density plot illustrating distributions of the area under the receiver operating curve (AUC) obtained from predictive model for coronary artery disease (CAD) diagnosed in the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study participants using traditional CVD risk factors without (reference model) and with the addition of genetic risk scores for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) (test model) over 1000 bootstraps. B. Distribution of differences in the area under the receiver operating curve (Δ AUC) obtained from predictive model for coronary artery disease (CAD) diagnosed in the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study participants using traditional CVD risk factors without and with the addition of genetic risk scores for coronary artery calcification (CAC GRS) over 1000 bootstraps. (Test model: $CAD \sim CAC\ GRS + age + sex + systolic\ blood\ pressure + total\ cholesterol + HDL\ cholesterol + smoking\ habit + medication\ for\ hypertension$. Reference model: $CAD \sim age + sex + systolic\ blood\ pressure + total\ cholesterol + HDL\ cholesterol + smoking\ habit + medication\ for\ hypertension$.)

Based on the results from three different European cohorts, this study showed that CAC GRS is a new risk marker for CAD. The CAC GRS had statistically significant added predictive value over the traditional CVD risk factors, improves prediction accuracy of the state-of-the-art GRS for CAD and, therefore, can play a crucial role in primary prevention of CVD.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pashupati P. Mishra: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Binisha H. Mishra:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Leo-Pekka Lyytikäinen:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Sirkka Goebeler:** Resources. **Mika Martiskainen:** Resources. **Emma Hakamaa:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Marcus E. Kleber:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Graciela E. Delgado:** Writing – review & editing. **Winfried März:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Mika Kähönen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Pekka J. Karhunen:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Terho Lehtimäki:** Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ajpc.2024.100884](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajpc.2024.100884).

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